

Formation of Thorium-Sulphosalicylate Complex

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Salicylic acid and its derivatives have been reported to undergo chelation with a large number of metals. Sulphosalicylic acid is known to form complexes with bivalent manganese¹, copper², aluminium³, and beryllium⁴. The present communication deals with the reaction between sulphosalicylic acid and thorium ion.

Thorium nitrate, $\text{Th}(\text{NO}_3)_4 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, and sulphosalicylic acid used were of B. D. H. AnalaR and E. Merck quality, respectively.

A Doran conductivity bridge and a Beckman glass electrode pH meter were used for conductance and pH measurement respectively, the temperature being maintained at 28°.

The reaction was studied by applying the monovariation method⁵ using equimolar solutions of thorium nitrate and salicylic acid of $M/40$ and $M/80$ strength. The observed conductance and pH data for $M/40$ solutions, plotted against the volume of the ligand, are shown in Fig. 1.

FIG. 1

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The plots show a clear break at 1:1 stoichiometry of the complex. Similar results were obtained for $M/80$ solutions also.

Application of Job's method of continued variation⁶ to measurements of conductance, using reactants $M/40$, $M/80$, and $M/120$ in strength, confirmed the above observation (Fig. 2).

FIG. 2

The dissociation constants of the thorium-sulphosalicylate chelate, as determined by Job's method⁶, are shown in Table I.

TABLE I

C	p	α	K calc.
$M/100$	2.0	0.417	3.80×10^{-3}
$M/100$	2.5	0.387	3.71
$M/100$	4.0	0.325	3.72

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